

Cloud-based Platform-agnostic Adversarial AI Defence framework

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Abstract—The exponential growth of Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies has significantly enhanced various domains, from smart cities to medical devices. However, this rapid advancement has also broadened the attack surface, leading to increased exposure to adversarial threats such as poisoning, evasion, inference, and extraction attacks. To address these challenges, we propose cPAID, a Cloud-based Platform-Agnostic Adversarial AI Defense framework designed to fortify AI systems against a wide range of adversarial attacks. The proposed framework integrates multiple defensive mechanisms, including Generative Adversarial AI, AI-assisted Intrusion Detection and Prevention Systems (AIPS), Risk Management for AI (RIMA), Data Fabric, Meta-SIEM (mSIEM), and Adversarial AI Cyber Range. Furthermore, the cPAID platform employs the MLPrivSecOps methodology, embedding security-, privacy-, and trust-by-design principles throughout the AI lifecycle. This paper presents the architecture, methodologies, and components of cPAID, emphasizing its scalability, robustness, and compliance with ethical AI principles.

Index Terms—AI, ML, Adversarial AI, Generative AI

I. INTRODUCTION

The exponential growth of data and advancements in computational technologies have accelerated the integration of AI across various domains, impacting everyday life, industries, and critical infrastructures. AI-driven systems are now foundational to cutting-edge innovations such as smart cities, autonomous ships, 5G-powered drones, and intelligent medical devices. The effectiveness of these systems relies heavily on Machine Learning (ML) and DL algorithms, which process extensive datasets to support essential decision-making processes. For instance, autonomous ships utilize AI-enabled sensors to analyze environmental conditions and dynamically adjust navigation, enhancing safety and efficiency. However, the deployment of AI in high-stakes environments introduces substantial risks, where even minor inaccuracies can result in severe consequences, including potential loss of life. As ML and Deep Learning (DL) technologies increasingly replace traditional approaches with AI-driven solutions, early adopters,

particularly organizations and industries, face heightened exposure to significant security threats. These threats include 0-day vulnerabilities, data integrity breaches, and model theft, largely due to inadequate tactical and strategic measures for safeguarding AI-based systems. The expanding utilization of AI technologies has consequently broadened the associated threat landscape, resulting in the emergence of a novel attack surface known as adversarial AI attacks. These attacks leverage various techniques to compromise the robustness of AI systems, ranging from evasion attacks—where adversarial inputs are introduced during the ML and DL model testing phase—to poisoning attacks, which embed malicious samples within training datasets. Such attacks undermine the integrity and reliability of AI systems, rendering them attractive targets for threat actors. To address these challenges, cPAID (Cloud-based Platform-Agnostic AI Defense) envisions developing a comprehensive, cloud-based, platform-agnostic defense framework aimed at fortifying AI applications against adversarial threats. The primary objective of cPAID is to mitigate [1] the impact of both poisoning and evasion attacks by integrating a diverse array of defensive strategies, including AI-assisted anomaly detection, ML-based Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS), feature reduction, adversarial training, and the implementation of security- and privacy-by-design principles. Furthermore, cPAID emphasizes the incorporation of explainable AI (XAI), Generative AI, context-awareness, risk and vulnerability assessment, and threat intelligence to enhance the robustness of AI systems. Additionally, cPAID aims to achieve the following objectives:

- Integrating security and privacy by design in the AI pipeline.
- Evaluating ML/DL robustness against adversarial threats.
- Aligning with EU AI ethics for responsible deployment.
- Validating cPAID components in real-world scenarios.

Ultimately, cPAID aims to support the creation of certification schemes that validate the robustness, security, privacy, and ethical soundness of AI systems. This framework promotes the deployment of trustworthy and resilient AI across diverse sectors.

II. RELATED WORK

A. Generative AI for adversarial attack generation

The rapid advancements in the AI domain have also given rise to sophisticated adversarial attacks, with hundreds of attack methods proposed in recent years [2]. Adversarial attacks are generally categorized into four types: (a) Poisoning Attacks, where an adversary targets the learning phase of ML and DL models to compromise their training process, (b) Inference Attacks, aiming to extract sensitive information about the training data, (c) Evasion Attacks, where arbitrary inputs are injected during the testing phase to mislead the model, and (d) Extraction Attacks, where an adversary attempts to recreate or replicate a model by exploiting its outputs. A prominent adversarial attack strategy involves gradient-based techniques that introduce perturbations to training data to generate adversarial samples. Several well-known methods in this category include C&W [3], FGSM [4], JSMA [5], and DeepFool [6]. Furthermore, learning-based frameworks such as DeepSniffer [7] have been developed to extract complete model architecture information by learning the relationship between architectural hints and the model's internal structures. Additionally, Label-only membership inference attacks have emerged as a technique that evaluates the robustness of model predictions by using perturbed inputs, rendering them effective against defense mechanisms relying on obfuscating confidence scores [8]. In 2022, the development of Generative AI models became a significant milestone in digital transformation, particularly due to the evolution of large language models (LLMs) such as ChatGPT and Bard. These models have demonstrated remarkable capabilities in various tasks, including generating text, images, code, audio, and video [9]. However, the application of Generative AI in cybersecurity remains underexplored, with most efforts focusing on data augmentation. For instance, Kumar et al. [10] employed Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) to generate synthetic attack data aimed at addressing the class imbalance problem in intrusion detection systems. Similarly, Peppes et al. [11] utilized GANs to generate botnet data in a tabular format, achieving an 80% similarity with real botnet attacks. Moreover, LLMs have been applied to generate highly realistic phishing email campaigns, which closely resemble benign communications and effectively evade traditional detection mechanisms [12].

B. AI systems' robustness improvement.

Machine Learning Operations (MLOps) is an emerging discipline that aims to streamline the development, deployment, and maintenance of ML systems by integrating development and operational processes, much like the foundational principles of DevOps. The primary focus of MLOps is on ensuring continuous automation, seamless integration, and robust

monitoring throughout the lifecycle of an ML system—from its initial design and testing to deployment and infrastructure management. Despite its importance, the principles of *Privacy* and *Security* often receive less attention compared to *Performance*, *Interpretability*, and *Interoperability* in the MLOps paradigm [13]. This imbalance prioritizes the efficiency and performance of AI systems over their security, privacy, and trustworthiness, inadvertently creating vulnerabilities that adversaries can exploit. Consequently, AI systems developed under the current MLOps framework are more susceptible to adversarial attacks due to insufficient emphasis on security and privacy considerations. Recognizing these deficiencies, researchers have increasingly advocated for the establishment of best practices aimed at developing secure and privacy-aware AI systems. Integrating security- and privacy-by-design principles into the MLOps pipeline is essential for building resilient AI systems capable of withstanding adversarial threats and maintaining trustworthiness throughout their lifecycle.

C. AI-driven adversarial attack detection.

The defense mechanisms against adversarial attacks on AI systems can be broadly categorized into two main approaches: (a) Mitigation, which focuses on enhancing model robustness to improve resilience against adversarial attacks, and (b) Detection, which involves employing ML and DL models to identify adversarial activities. While the mitigation approach has been extensively explored in the literature, research dedicated to adversarial attack detection has only recently gained attention, and thus the current state-of-the-art (SoA) remains in its early stages. Existing approaches for detecting adversarial attacks often involve deploying auxiliary ML models trained through various learning paradigms, including supervised learning [14], self-supervised learning [15], and federated learning [16]. Additionally, distance-based techniques, such as Euclidean distance calculations, are used to measure discrepancies between normal and adversarial examples. These distance metrics are commonly combined with machine learning classifiers like Random Forests, Support Vector Machines (SVMs), and Logistic Regression to detect adversarial instances [17]. Furthermore, frameworks like Adversarial Robustness Toolbox (ART) [18] provide a comprehensive environment for testing ML and DL models against various types of adversarial attacks. ART also offers a limited set of basic defense mechanisms aimed at protecting AI models from adversarial threats. Despite these efforts, a significant limitation of existing adversarial detection techniques is their dependency on specific attacks or model architectures. For instance, a method designed to detect label-flipping attacks may not be effective against membership inference attacks. This model- and attack-dependence highlights the need for more generalized and adaptable detection solutions that can effectively protect AI systems across diverse threat scenarios.

D. Adversarial risk management & threat intelligence

Effectively defending AI systems from malicious actors is becoming increasingly critical, and accurate risk assessment

is a fundamental precursor to implementing robust defense mechanisms. One proposed approach [19] introduces a risk assessment model combining the AI Act framework with methodologies inspired by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change and literature. This model estimates the magnitude of AI-related risks by evaluating the interplay between three primary components: (a) Risk Determinants, (b) Drivers of Determinants, and (c) Various Risk Types. Additionally, a comprehensive Risk Management Framework [20] has been proposed for AI systems, structured around four measurable principles: Sustainability, Accuracy, Fairness, and Explainability. This framework provides a structured approach to assessing and mitigating potential risks associated with AI systems. Moreover, a holistic approach to risk assessment [21] has been developed to evaluate different types of inference attacks, including membership inference, model inversion, attribute inference, and model stealing. This methodology establishes a detailed threat model taxonomy and leverages defensive mechanisms to quantify mitigation effectiveness. Furthermore, another study [22] introduces a novel scoring system designed to assess the risk posed by adversarial machine learning threats. This scoring system assigns severity scores to various attacks, offering a practical tool for evaluating and prioritizing potential threats to AI systems.

E. Context awareness of AI systems.

Context awareness refers to an intelligent system’s ability to gather, interpret, and analyze relevant information from its environment to make well-informed decisions or provide more suitable responses [23]. A proposed framework [24] addresses the classification of industry-specific context types, demonstrating its applicability through an industry-oriented use case. This framework aids in the systematic implementation of context-aware systems by defining and categorizing different contextual dimensions. Research on context-awareness has been explored across various domains, including digital twins [25], energy management [26], and failure management [27]. While context-awareness is recognized as a critical component in applications that involve automated decision-making, its integration into the AI domain remains underexplored and inadequately discussed. The lack of thorough examination and standardization in AI-related context-awareness presents a significant challenge that must be addressed to enhance robustness and adaptability in intelligent systems.

F. Adversarial AI cyber range.

Adversarial AI cyber ranges [28] are essential tools for creating realistic environments to evaluate, develop, and enhance the robustness of AI systems against adversarial threats. One notable example is the Splunk Attack Range [29], an open-source project that enables security teams to rapidly deploy detection development environments designed to emulate adversarial behavior. The generated telemetry data from these environments supports the creation and testing of effective detection mechanisms. Similarly, SimuLand [30] is an open-source framework that facilitates the deployment of lab en-

vironments mimicking real-world attack scenarios. This tool allows researchers to actively test and validate the effectiveness of various security solutions, such as Microsoft 365 Defender, Azure Defender, and Microsoft Sentinel. Additionally, SimuLand offers the capability to extend threat research through telemetry and forensic artifacts generated during simulation exercises. Furthermore, another cyber range [31] has been developed to support agile reconfigurations, enabling a wide range of experiments focused on evaluating cybersecurity tools involving AI and ML. This testbed provides realistic environments with the capability to programmatically observe and collect data during experiments. Its design also supports the reproducibility of evaluations, allowing for consistent comparisons of different tools and techniques over time.

III. cPAID PLATFORM

The **cPAID** platform offers a comprehensive approach to AI security by integrating defense methods, code development, security assessments, event management, and context-awareness. Unlike traditional solutions focused only on training or detection, cPAID addresses the entire AI pipeline to combat evolving adversarial threats.

From design to deployment, cPAID focuses on early threat detection using DevPrivSecOps, anomaly detection, penetration testing, risk management, and cyber ranges, all tailored for AI. This scalable, cloud-based solution uses containerized components for seamless integration. At its core, MLPrivSecOps strengthens MLOps by embedding security and privacy principles early in AI development.

The GenAAI module uses Generative AI models, such as LLMs and Digital Twins, to simulate adversarial attacks for resilience testing. The AI-assisted Intrusion Detection and Prevention System into a unified interface based on a data-as-a-product model.

The Adversarial AI Cyber Range trains professionals through hands-on attack scenarios, while Meta-SIEM consolidates alerts and system-wide security insights. Together, modules like AIPS, RIMA, GenAAI, Data Fabric, mSIEM, and the Cyber Range ensure robust, collaborative protection across the AI lifecycle.

A. MLPrivSecOps

The **MLPrivSecOps** module of the cPAID platform enhances MLOps by embedding *security-, privacy-, and trust-by-design principles* throughout **Continuous Integration, Continuous Delivery, and Continuous Training**. By integrating **DevPrivSecOps** with MLOps, it equips AI developers with tools to build resilient AI systems against adversarial attacks. The module incorporates security mechanisms across the AI pipeline, including *data collection, analysis, feature extraction, code development, resource management, and monitoring*. Key techniques like **adversarial training, defensive distillation, and feature reduction** enhance model robustness. Additionally, it strengthens training data security by detecting and countering *data poisoning attacks*, especially from third-party sources. **XAI** tools such as **SHAP** and **LIME**

provide insights into model performance, assisting in algorithm selection and reducing trial-and-error development. To address security vulnerabilities in third-party packages, ML-PrivSecOps employs **Software Bill of Materials** to generate an **AI Bill of Materials**. Enhanced monitoring is achieved through *context-awareness mechanisms* that adapt models to changing environments by monitoring contextual shifts. *Self-improvement and self-adaptation mechanisms* are incorporated through **life-long learning**, allowing AI systems to adjust their behavior for continuous robustness. The **MLPrivSecOps module** establishes guidelines for advancing MLOps with *security, privacy, and trust-by-design principles*, along with *context-awareness practices*, enabling organizations to achieve certified robustness, security, and adaptability under the **cPAID secure MLOps standard**.

B. cPAID Generative Adversarial AI (GenAAI)

The **GenAAI** within the cPAID platform offers a framework for generating adversarial attack vectors by utilizing **GAN** and **LLMs**. While extensively applied across various domains, Generative AI's potential for creating realistic adversarial attacks remains underexplored. The GenAAI leverages these models to generate synthetic attacks by analyzing and synthesizing large datasets. The GenAAI module focuses on creating realistic adversarial attacks across **poisoning, evasion, inference, and extraction** categories, informed by three primary data sources: (i) *Comprehensive Taxonomy of Adversarial Attacks*, detailing attack types, targeted models, and success indicators; (ii) *Detected Adversarial Attacks* from the **cPAID Data Fabric**, enhancing training for GAN and LLM models; and (iii) *Attacker's Knowledge*, categorized as **White-Box, Gray-Box, and Black-Box Attacks** based on the attacker's knowledge of the target system. The module prioritizes **white-box attacks** due to their effectiveness, but also considers **gray-box** and **black-box** scenarios to test resilience under limited information. GenAAI further improves its methods by continuously refining synthetic attacks through training with data obtained from the **AI-Assisted Adversarial Intrusion Detection and Prevention System (AIPS)** and stored in the **cPAID Data Fabric**. Generated attacks are validated through **Digital Twin** testing to ensure their realism and effectiveness before being used to train or retrain models. The **GenAAI module** provides a critical mechanism for evaluating, enhancing, and ensuring AI system robustness against evolving adversarial threats.

C. AI-assisted Adversarial Intrusion Detection and Prevention System

The **AI-assisted Adversarial Intrusion Detection and Prevention System (AIPS)** within cPAID combines **Deep Neural Networks (DNNs)**, such as **CNNs** and **RNNs**, with *Ensemble Classification* techniques to enhance detection accuracy and robustness. Techniques like **stacking** and **soft/hard-voting** ensemble learning enable efficient monitoring of network traffic to detect adversarial attacks. AIPS enhances performance and resilience through **life-long learning**, **semi-supervised**

learning, and **reinforcement learning**. Life-long learning dynamically trains DNN models with new information from the **cPAID Data Fabric** [32], [33], including data from **GenAAI** and previously detected attacks. Semi-supervised learning allows training with minimal labeled data, while **Reinforcement Learning**, using **Deep Q Learning**, improves adaptability and robustness by learning from interactions with the environment. The module also integrates **Federated Learning** and **Transfer Learning** to ensure adaptability and privacy across different cPAID implementations. AIPS actively monitors network traffic for anomalies, blocking detected adversarial attacks at the network level to ensure enhanced security. The **AIPS** module provides organizations with a robust, adaptive solution for AI system protection through continuous learning, anomaly detection, and collaborative defense mechanisms.

D. mSIEM

The **Meta-SIEM** module of cPAID enhances traditional SIEM systems by integrating *semi-supervised learning* for incident categorization and **XAI** for improved interpretability. It establishes secure communication with **AIPS** to monitor network and system activities, collecting detected anomalies for analysis. Using **DNNs** and *semi-supervised learning*, mSIEM categorizes incidents while **XAI** ensures human operators can make informed decisions. **Statistical analysis** methods like **Z-score algorithms** set thresholds for metrics, triggering alerts when exceeded. Real-time data processing and customized ML models enhance rapid threat response. mSIEM aggregates data from **AIPS**, **GenAAI**, **RIMA**, **Data Fabric**, and the **Adversarial Cyber Range**. Clustering techniques (**K-Means**, **DBSCAN**) and anomaly detection methods (**Isolation Forest**, **Autoencoders**) detect patterns and potential threats. The module integrates *AI/ML algorithms* with ticketing systems, automating incident generation and alert escalation via *NLP* and *Decision Trees*. **AI-driven playbooks** streamline response workflows, improving threat management efficiency. The **mSIEM** module leverages open-source tools like the **ELK Stack** and **Wazuh** for continuous monitoring, incident management, and threat detection across cPAID components.

E. RIMA

The **RIMA** within cPAID provides quantitative assessment and mitigation of cyber risks in AI systems. Its core functions include **risk identification**, **risk management**, and **risk mitigation**. **Risk Identification** employs tools like:

- **ptAI**: Uses the **GenAAI module**, **Nmap**, and **Metasploit** for attack simulation.
- **AIVAS**: Detects vulnerabilities through **tokenization** and **AST construction**.
- **AIsoDog**: Generates phishing scenarios using **NLG** to assess user susceptibility.

Risk Management is handled by the **AI-based Harmonization (AIH)** module, which aggregates data from **ptAI**, **AIVAS**, and **AIsoDog** using the **Elastic Platform**. It uses a quantitative approach incorporating human expertise and continuous lifelong learning for enhanced adaptability. **Risk Mitigation** is

performed by the **Alerting System (ALY)**, which continuously monitors and compares risk data with historical data stored in the **cPAID Data Fabric**. Alerts are generated when threats are detected. AIH and ALY ensure compliance with the **NIST AI Risk Management Framework**. The **RIMA** provides strategies for defending against adversarial attacks and suggests appropriate mitigation methods. Once all identified risks are addressed, the system becomes eligible for the **cPAID AI-risk-free certificate**. This structured approach offers a robust solution for assessing and managing risks associated with adversarial threats to AI systems.

F. Data Fabric

The cPAID’s **Data Fabric** provides a *metadata-driven architecture* design to support a seamless integration of multiple data types from heterogeneous sources and expose them through a standardized interface. As modern AI systems require vast amounts of training data from diverse sources, the cPAID Data Fabric addresses it ensuring high availability, traceability, and responsible data usage across the platform.

The Data Fabric facilitates *data governance activities*, ensuring that data is properly managed and securely accessible to authorized modules. To achieve this, the Data Fabric employs advanced technologies such as **knowledge graphs**, which offer a promising approach for building robust data fabric architectures. By adhering to the principles of the *data mesh paradigm*, the Data Fabric follows a *data-as-a-product approach*, where raw data is transformed into high-quality data products that can be easily discovered, trusted, and accessed by various consumers such as **GenAAI**, **AIPS**, and **Meta-SIEM**.

Additionally, the Data Fabric integrates **authentication and access control mechanisms**, including **OpenID Connect**, **Attribute-Based Access Control**, and **Role-Based Access Control**, to ensure data confidentiality, integrity, and availability by granting access exclusively to authorized data consumers [34], [35]. By leveraging **knowledge graph technologies**, the Data Fabric implements an approach based on *semantic data products*, enabling efficient integration of data from various sources and providing them to authorized consumers through a standardized interface.

Ultimately, the **Data Fabric Module** of cPAID offers a scalable, secure, and efficient framework for managing and governing data, ensuring the reliability and robustness of AI systems operating within the cPAID platform.

G. Adversarial AI Cyber-Range

The **Adversarial AI Cyber-Range Module** in cPAID enables cross-disciplinary collaboration, AI security evaluation, and incident response training through simulated adversarial attacks. It offers a cost-effective training environment for enhancing security and ensuring compliance. Features include:

- **Vulnerable AI System Simulation:** Hands-on training via *Capture The Flag (CTF)* frameworks for defensive and offensive AI security exercises.

- **Red Team-Blue Team Exercises:** Attack-defense scenarios where the *Red Team* exploits AI vulnerabilities and the *Blue Team* mitigates them.
- **AI-Enhanced Social Engineering:** Simulations involving AI-generated content for deception and user-awareness training.
- **AI in IoT Security:** Scenarios addressing security challenges in AI-driven IoT devices.

The module supports individual and large-scale exercises using *CTF-like scoring* for performance evaluation and training effectiveness. It adheres to frameworks like the *Serious Games Design Framework* and the *Gamification Design Framework*. Tools like **GameMaker**, **Construct**, **Phaser3**, and **Quest** provide engaging, interactive scenarios for training. Training occurs in a *sandbox environment*, promoting safe experimentation and skill development. Successful participants receive the **cPAID Cyber Range Certificate**, certifying competence in detecting and mitigating adversarial AI attacks.

Fig. 1. cPAID’s Envisioned platform.

IV. CONCLUSION

cPAID offers a platform-agnostic approach to secure AI systems against adversarial attacks. By integrating modules such as GenAAI, AIPS, RIMA, Data Fabric, mSIEM, and Adversarial AI Cyber Range, cPAID provides a holistic defense strategy that addresses various aspects of AI security (i.e., attack detection, risk management, and response training). The implementation of the MLPrivSecOps methodology ensures that security, privacy, and trust considerations are embedded throughout the AI development lifecycle, enhancing robustness and resilience. Ultimately, cPAID aims to establish itself as a benchmark framework for adversarial AI defense, promoting the development of trustworthy and resilient AI systems across industries.

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